

Geospatial assessment of *Jatropha curcas* plantation in Qatar: A GIS modelling approach

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Abstract

Qatar is one of the largest producers and exporters of fossil-based fuels including natural gas. Though, the country is striving to diversify its energy resources by incorporating renewables to mitigate associated emissions and expand its fossil reserves lifetime for the coming generations. Energy crops are believed to be amongst the prominent resource for biofuel production for being carbon neutral. However, no attempts were made to grow energy crops due to the extremely limited arable land area as well as the water scarcity in this part of the world. Meanwhile, *Jatropha curcas* is preferred over other energy crops due to its superior agronomical traits, where it can grow in non-arable lands and harsh climates with minimal water requirements. Besides, it proved to yield higher seeds with the supply of treated sewage effluent, which is widely available and not completely utilised in Qatar. According to the UN's Food and Agricultural Organisation, *Jatropha* can grow within 30°N and 35°S latitudes. Yet, there is a need to investigate suitable sites to grow *Jatropha* across Qatar. As such, this study utilises the Geographic Information System (GIS) and Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to identify the suitable sites based on multicriteria including soil type, depth and pH contents, as well as average annual humidity and temperature. The combination of these methods and criteria may provide a better insight on the potential of biofuel production from *Jatropha* in Qatar. The GIS-based spatial analysis identified wasteland area of 6779 km² in Qatar as highly suitable to grow *Jatropha*. In addition, 1564 km² are identified as moderately suitable sites. The obtained results indicate a high potential to grow *Jatropha* in Qatar for biofuel production with no competition on land and water resources.

Keywords: Qatar, *Jatropha curcas*, GIS, Geospatial modeling, Site suitability, Biofuel.

I. Introduction

Qatar is a peninsula located in the Arabian Gulf with an area of ~11,500 km² and an elevation of below 100 m above the sea level. Its arid-desert climate is characterised by an average daily temperature of 13 – 42 °C (Cheng et al., 2017), a highly fluctuating rainfall of about 80 mm (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2008), a strong wind and a high relative humidity (Abu Sukar et al., 2007). While evapotranspiration ranges from as low as 2 mm/day in December, up to 10 mm/day in June (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2008).

The arable area in Qatar is about 65,000 ha, which is only 0.6% of the country's total area (Department of Agricultural and Water Research, 2002). Besides, the soils of Qatar belongs to "aridisol" category that distinguish the areas of an arid climate (Qatar Statistics Authority, 2013). Four types of soil are found in Qatar including rawdha, lithosol, sabkha and sandy soil (Ministry of Municipal Affairs and Agriculture, 2005). Rawdha soil or farm soil is found in around 850 land depressions, and made up of sandy-loam, sandy-clay-loam or calcareous-loam, with a depth of 30-150 cm. Whereas lithosol is a shallow soil with a typical depth of (10-30 cm), composed of calcareous-sandy-loam and mostly covered with limestone and rock debris. Sandy soil is composed of coarse-sand and calcareous-loamy-sand with a considerable depth of at least 120 cm (Baalousha, 2016). Besides, sabkha soil is a highly saline soil that is found in coastal areas and mainly composed of clay, slit and mud with a considerable depth (Baalousha, 2016; Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2008).

Meanwhile, Qatar is suffering from land degradation, whereby 191,000 ha of its arable lands were affected by wind erosion, while this area is gradually increasing due to the movement of sand dunes towards agricultural and populated areas (Abahussain et al., 2002). Nevertheless, dust or sandstorms are a regular phenomenon in the Arabian Peninsula (Hermida et al., 2018). This phenomenon results in severe health problems, crop damages, traffic accidents, soil degradation, solar systems malfunction and disorder in many public sectors (Beegum et al., 2018).

On the other hand, Qatar has one of the highest GDP per capita worldwide (TheWorldBank, 2019), with oil and natural gas being the main source of the government revenues (US-Qatar Business Council, 2018). Although Qatar has the third largest proven reserve of natural gas, the country strives to invest in renewables to diversify its energy resources and mitigate its carbon footprint. Whereby, Qatar's GHG emissions have increased with an annual average of 6.38% over the period 1999-2018 (Knoema, 2018a).

Energy crops are the most prominent source of carbon-neutral energy. Though, due to the poor soil and harsh climate of Qatar, no attempts to grow energy crops have been made earlier to the best knowledge of the authors. However, *Jatropha curcas* proved to be one of the most promising energy crops that tolerates arid climates and thrives in marginal and non-arable lands, leaving fertile soils for food crops (Singh et al., 2008; Tomar et al., 2014). The Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) revealed that *Jatropha* can best thrive within 30°N and 35°S latitudes (Ismail and Rossi, 2010), as such, it is believed to have the potential to grow in Qatar. Furthermore, *Jatropha* has been used earlier to enhance soil, mitigate wind erosion and as a live fence (Tomar et al., 2014). While the *Jatropha* fruit and oil can be utilised to produce different fuel products (Alherbawi et al., 2020a, 2020b). Therefore, as an added value, *Jatropha* can be grown in Qatar for multiple purposes; not only for biofuel production, but also to preserve the soil against wind erosion, combat desertification and sandstorms and enhance the air quality by capturing carbon emissions and dust.

Jatropha can grow in different soil types including saline, arid and marginal lands (Prasad et al., 2017; Tomar et al., 2014). However, well-aerated sandy-loam or clay-loam soils with good drainage and a pH of 5.2-8.5 are reported to contribute to higher yields (Tomar et al., 2014). Clay soils may limit root system development (Valdés-Rodríguez et al., 2013), while salinity may suppress the *Jatropha* fruit yield (Tomar et al., 2014). Preliminary site assessment is crucial to ensure the success of *Jatropha* biofuel projects, as the lack of sufficient agronomic experience was the main reason behind the failure of different projects earlier (Wahl et al., 2012). In this regard, the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) has emerged as an effective tool for multicriteria weighing and is being increasingly used for optimal sites selection (Taddese, 2014). Meanwhile, several GIS-based spatial assessments of *Jatropha curcas* have been conducted in different countries including Brazil (Yamada and Sentelhas, 2014), Ethiopia (Taddese, 2014), India (Sunil et al., 2009), Malaysia (Shabanimofrad et al., 2011), Pakistan (Khan and Hasan, 2020) and Thailand (Qasim et al., 2015). While Trabucco et al. (Trabucco et al., 2010) conducted a global mapping of *Jatropha* yields in response to different climates.

Since *Jatropha curcas* has never been cultivated before in Qatar, there is a need to evaluate the land suitability to grow it prior to actual plantation trials. As such, this study utilises the geographic information system (ArcGIS) combined with the AHP decision-making tool to select *Jatropha* plantation sites that may possibly contribute to the highest yields. Identification of optimal plantation sites may provide a broader insight on the potential of biofuel production, carbon capture and soil enhancement through the cultivation of *Jatropha* in Qatar.

II. Methodology

The key criteria that are expected to influence the growth and yield of *Jatropha* in Qatar are selected carefully based on published cultivation experiences worldwide and considering the topographic and climate conditions. The selected factors include soil type, depth and pH, as well as the average annual temperature and humidity.

The annual precipitation is not considered in this study due to the limited and highly fluctuating levels, therefore, an irrigated *Jatropha* crop is assumed. While other topographic features such as land elevation and slope are also ignored due to their marginal variations. Besides, the ranges of the key factors are grouped into three classes of suitability, labelled as: highly suitable, moderately suitable, and marginally suitable as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Definition of key criteria and their ranges (adapted from (Alherbawi et al., 2021; Maes et al., 2009; Tomar et al., 2014; Trabucco et al., 2010; Valdés-Rodríguez et al., 2013)).

Criteria		Suitability classes		
		Highly suitable	Moderately suitable	Marginally suitable
Soil factors	Soil type	Rawdha/Lithosol	Sandy	Sabkha
	Soil depth (cm)	>45	20-45	<20
	Soil pH	5.5 – 8.5	4.5 – 5.5, 8.5 – 9.5	<4.5 & >9.5
Climate factors	Annual average temperature (°C)	<28	28-38	>38
	Annual average Humidity (%)	>60	40-60	<40

The relative importance of the selected criteria is evaluated using analytical hierarchy process (AHP) (Saaty, 1999). Whereby a pair-wise comparison is conducted as presented in Table 2. The AHP tool facilitates the breakdown of complex problems into a hierarchical structure, in which the qualitative and quantitative aspects of the problem are collectively considered (Haji et al., 2020). Initially, each criterion in the extreme left column of the pair-wise matrix is compared with the criteria in the top row in terms of their importance in the problem and is given a value based on the extent of importance. 1 is given for equal importance, 3 for moderate importance, 5 for strong importance, 7 for very strong importance and 9 for extreme importance.

The normalised pair-wise comparison is then estimated by dividing each element in the matrix by the sum of its own column. Finally, the average of each row in the normalised matrix is calculated which represents the weight of the corresponding criterion in the row.

Table 2: AHP's pair-wise comparison matrix.

Criteria	Soil type	Soil depth	Soil pH	Temp.	Humidity
Soil type	1.00	3.00	7.00	5.00	5.00
Soil depth	0.33	1.00	5.00	3.00	5.00
Soil pH	0.14	0.20	1.00	0.30	0.33
Temp.	0.20	0.33	3.33	1.00	1.00
Humidity	0.20	0.20	3.00	1.00	1.00
Total	1.88	4.73	19.33	10.30	12.33

In addition, the consistency of the pair-wise comparison is tested and validated using consistency ratio approach developed by Saaty (1988) to ensure their suitability to be used in the decision-making process. Only consistency ratios (CR) below 10% are considered as acceptable values and indicate a reasonable consistency of the pair-wise comparison.

ArcGIS (V.10.7.1) is used to plot five maps representing the selected criteria with three suitability classes based on data retrieved from Qatar Atlas (Qatar Statistics Authority, 2013) and the Atlas of soils for the State of Qatar (Ministry of Municipal Affairs and Agriculture, 2005), as well as the geospatial network of the UN’s Food and Agriculture Organisation (Food and Agriculture Organisation, 2020). While a composite suitability map is generated considering the criteria weights that are estimated earlier using the following formula (Taddese, 2016):

$$\text{Site suitability} = \sum_{i=1}^5 (W_i \times C_i) \tag{1}$$

Where, W_i : is the relative weight of criterion C_i

III. Results and discussion

The obtained AHP’s criteria weights are presented in Table 3. The process granted soil types the highest importance with approximately 50%, followed by the soil depth. While the average annual temperature and humidity are given almost equal importance. Besides, the criteria pair-wise comparison achieved a consistency ratio of 5%, which indicate a reasonable consistency.

Table 3: Definition of criteria weight using AHP.

Criteria	Soil type	Soil depth	Temp.	Humidity	Soil pH
Criteria weight	0.48	0.27	0.11	0.10	0.05
Ranking	1	2	3	4	5

Soil type and depth are the decisive factors in identifying the optimal plantation sites. Whereby, temperature and humidity have minimal variation across the different locations. While the pH of Qatar’s soil falls within the high suitability range for *Jatropha*.

The generated composite suitability map is presented in Fig.1. Where the high suitability sites dominated around 75% of the evaluated area.

The GIS-model identified around 6779 km² of the total Qatar area as highly suitable to grow *Jatropha*. The former figure accounts only for arid and wastelands and excludes the area of arable lands that are reserved for food cultivation (~650 km²). Besides, the model has also identified around 1564 km² as moderately suitable sites for *Jatropha* cultivation. While the remaining area showed low suitability mainly due to soil salinity, as well as limited depth which may suppress the fruit yield and limit roots development, respectively. The northern part of Qatar exhibited higher suitability as compared to the southern part, while the central region has shown better performance than the coastal areas.

Considering a fruit yield of 10 tonnes/ha, the area which is identified as highly suitable can generate over 6.5 million tonnes of *Jatropha* biomass, including 1.7 million tonnes of oil per year. Upon upgrading, the oil alone can perfectly cover the gasoline demand in the state of Qatar, which is estimated by 1.25 million tonnes/year (Knoema, 2018b). As such, *Jatropha curcas* is proved to have a high potential to be utilised in the State of Qatar as a carbon sink and an alternative source of energy.

Fig.1: Composite suitability map of *Jatropha* in Qatar.

IV. Conclusions

This study utilised the Geographic Information System (GIS) and Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to identify the optimal cultivation sites of *Jatropha curcas* in Qatar based on multicriteria including soil type, depth and pH contents, as well as average annual humidity and temperature. The GIS-based spatial analysis identified wasteland area of 6779 km² in Qatar as highly suitable to grow *Jatropha*. In addition, 1564 km² are identified as moderately suitable sites. The highly suitable sites can possibly generate over 1.7 million tonnes of oil, which is sufficient to completely meet the gasoline demand of Qatar. As such, *Jatropha curcas* showed high potential to be cultivated in Qatar for biofuel production and GHG emissions mitigation.

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